

Undeniable Opportunity or Death Trap?

The Effects of Digital Transformation and Big Tech Companies on Small Businesses

Mike van Ballegooijen
Tilburg University
m.b.vanballegooijen@tilburguniversity.edu

Maxim Klíma
Tilburg University
m.j.a.klíma@tilburguniversity.edu

Jordy van Veen
Tilburg University
j.vanveen_2@tilburguniversity.edu

Fenna Zegwaard
Tilburg University
f.zegwaard@tilburguniversity.edu

ABSTRACT

Measures taken by governments to combat the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in the increase of digital transformation. While many companies across all industries suffered greatly from these measures, Big Tech companies profited. It is largely unknown what effects the increased digital transformation and influence of Big Tech companies have on small businesses in the technology industry, resulting in a knowledge gap. Both archival and survey research have been conducted to reduce this gap by illustrating the existing knowledge and measuring the opinion of Dutch small businesses respectively.

The research concludes that digital transformation and Big Tech companies are beneficial for small businesses in the technology industry. Digital transformation has led to an extra dynamic industry and Big Tech companies are responsible for most technological developments and cause the entire technology industry to grow. However, it is crucial for small businesses to respond correctly to maximize the benefit of this growth.

KEYWORDS

Big Tech, small businesses, technology industry, digital transformation, COVID-19.

INTRODUCTION

Due to measures taken by international governments to combat the COVID-19 pandemic, such as lockdowns and working remotely, there has been an increase in the usage of digital technologies. This usage includes online shopping and social media (Akram et al., 2020). Internet traffic increased with 60% between December 2019 and May 2020, where videoconference traffic

increased around 120% since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic (Soto-Acosta, 2020). This increase has accelerated the digital transformation of companies and industries to respond to COVID-19 measures.

While many companies across all industries suffered greatly from these measures, Big Tech companies such as Google, Amazon, Facebook, Apple and Microsoft profited. Their attractiveness among consumers increased as they became the primary channels for individuals to receive information about COVID-19, communicate with others and shop online (Kshetri, 2020). Despite a projected potential loss of \$1.5 billion in the second quarter of this year, Amazon doubled its net profit from \$2.6 billion to \$5.2 billion between June 2019 and June 2020 respectively (Amazon, 2020). This example further illustrates the dominance of Big Tech companies across the digital landscape. Amazon's global e-commerce market share reached 13.7% in 2019, including 49% of the market in the United States. Google holds almost 90% of the worldwide desktop market share among leading search engines and Facebook dominates 74.6% of the global social media market (Clement, 2019; Clement, 2020; Statcounter, 2020).

The current dominance of Big Tech companies is the result of the uncharted territory they operate in (Moore, 2016). Many of the technological developments in the digital landscape, such as artificial intelligence (AI), are recent. It is impossible to fully predict how these developments are going to be used or improved in the future. With limited knowledge about future developments, appropriate legislation, including restrictions on merging and acquisitions to avoid consolidation of power, is difficult. When legislation, although rare, is possible, adoption by international governments can take years. Furthermore, low awareness among consumers about the dominance of Big Tech companies limits

the demand for change and allows for the dominance to grow. Lastly, some Big Tech companies make use of compatibility restrictions to increase the difficulty for consumers to switch to a competitor. Facebook made use of this tactic for a number of years by obligating consumers to log into their Facebook account in order to create a profile on the dating application Tinder (Timmermans & De Caluwé, 2010).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

While both the increase of digital transformation due to the COVID-19 measures and the current influence of Big Tech companies are clear, it is largely unknown what effects they have on small businesses in the technology industry.

Existing literature describes that many small businesses in the industry depend on Big Tech companies to offer and advertise their products and services. A small change in Google's algorithm can have devastating consequences for a small business (Soni et al, 2019). However, Big Tech companies lead the way in most technological developments, causing rapid growth in the technology industry. Small businesses could benefit from this growth (Moore, 2016).

Evidence of the conjectures stated above and to what extent the influence of Big Tech companies mediates the relationship between the increase of digital transformation and small businesses in the technology industry are missing, resulting in a knowledge gap. When the effects of increased digital transformation and influence of Big Tech companies on small businesses in the technology industry are clear, legislators can develop appropriate regulations regarding the current and future influence of Big Tech companies in the technology industry. Furthermore, reducing the knowledge gap offers governments insight into the effects of increased digital transformation on small businesses in this industry, which in turn can be used to offer tailored aid to these businesses when necessary.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To examine the effects of increased digital transformation and influence of Big Tech companies on small businesses in the technology industry, the following research question and supporting sub-questions have been developed:

“What effects do the increase of digital transformation and the influence of Big Tech companies have on small businesses in the technology industry, and to what extent is relationship between the increase of digital

transformation and small businesses in the technology industry mediated by the influence of Big Tech companies?”

Sub-questions:

1. *To what extent did Big Tech companies influence the technology industry before the increase of digital transformation?*
2. *What effect does the increase of digital transformation have on the technology industry?*
3. *To what extent did the increase of digital transformation affect small businesses in the technology industry?*
4. *To what extent are small businesses in the technology influenced by Big Tech companies?*

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual Model

In this research, digital transformation is defined as the collective process of using digital technologies to drive significant changes in the business model of companies operating in all industries (Fitzgerald et al., 2014).

Big Tech companies are defined as a handful of technology giants that dominate the digital market, namely Google, Amazon, Facebook, Apple and Microsoft (GAFAM) (Mayer-Schonberger & Ramge, 2018).

Small businesses are defined as companies with a staff headcount of less than fifty and an annual turnover or annual balance sheet total less than ten million euros (European Commission, 2020).

The technology industry consists of businesses that revolve around the manufacturing of electronics, creation of software, computers or products and services related to information technology (Frankenfield, 2019).

As stated earlier, measures taken by international governments to combat the COVID-19 outbreak resulted in the increase of digital transformation. This research investigates the direct effects of the increase of digital transformation and the influence of Big Tech companies on small businesses in the technology industry. Furthermore, the study also examines to what extent the effect of the increase of digital transformation on these small businesses is mediated by the influence of Big Tech companies.

Thus, the increase of digital transformation due to COVID-19 measures acts as the independent

variable of this research while small businesses in the technology industry act as the dependent variable. The influence of Big Tech companies is a partial mediator. The relationships between these variables are illustrated in the conceptual model below.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been formulated according to the conceptual model:

H1: The increase of digital transformation due to COVID-19 measures has an effect on small businesses in the technology industry.

H2: The influence of Big Tech companies has an effect on small businesses in the technology industry.

H3: The relationship between the increase of digital transformation due to COVID-19 measures and small businesses in the technology industry is mediated by the influence of Big Tech companies.

METHOD

To get a comprehensive overview of the knowledge gap, primary data (survey) and secondary data (archival research) is conducted in this research. The research has a deductive approach (also labeled as a testing theory) which develops hypotheses based on existing theory, and then designing a research strategy to test the hypotheses (Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2016). Archival research gives insights in external data. For this reason, archival research is used to answer the first two sub-questions. To ensure the archival research is valid, search engines such as 'Google Scholar', 'Business Source Ultimate' and mainly 'World Cat' were used. These different search engines were used to obtain the insights needed for this paper that consists of a relatively narrow scope. Furthermore, criteria such as year of publishing were searched upon, but not leading to the selection for articles. The main reason for this is that older articles do not directly mean the article is less valid. The scope can for instance be more fitting to the research of an older article.

To answer sub questions 3 and 4, a self-constructed survey (see Appendix 1) with

additional archival research is used. A survey is an effective way of collecting information (knowledge, attitudes and behavior) from people. The unit of analysis are organizations, in this case small businesses. The sampling method that is used is convenience sampling. Convenience sampling refers to the collection of information from members of the population, who are conveniently available to prove it (Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2016). This sampling method is used because it retrieves basic information quickly and efficiently. In this research, the population concerns small businesses in the technology industry in the Netherlands. Furthermore, the sampling frame consists of approximately 8.000 companies, and is obtained by using specific criteria in the database Orbis. The used criteria are as follows: *active companies, small size companies, in the Netherlands, the sector information technology and computer services*. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling design, which is appropriate for qualitative research. This type of sample is easier to access, but has a higher risk of sampling bias.

The survey consists of a short introduction in which the researchers introduce themselves, what the goal of this research is and how much time it should take to fill in the survey. After the introduction a couple of questions regarding personal data are asked, to make a distinction between specific fields a tech company operates. However, these personal questions are optional to secure privacy. The questions of the survey are based on a non-comparative scale, i.e. the Likert scale. Moreover, the questionnaire is concluded by showing appreciation and the option to leave an email address if the respondent is interested in the results or conference. The exact sample size that is used in this research consists of 48 respondents. To maximize the response rate, small businesses were randomly selected in Orbis, and contacted by phone. Moreover, the survey was only sent by email when interest was shown. Considering a total amount of 365 phone calls, a response rate of 13.2% can be adopted for this research.

Based on the survey, existing information from archival research can be confirmed, mutated and supplemented. Not to mention, the survey's validity can be measured on the basis of the amount of responses, and the questions that avoid social desirability bias due to leading or loading questions. Avoiding bias is done by stating the questions in a way that the negative influence of Big Tech isn't the obvious choice for small businesses. At last, the survey's reliability can be measured with the Cronbach Alpha-test. Further explanation about the validity and reliability will be reflected on in the discussion and limitations of this research.

RESULTS

To what extent did Big Tech companies influence the technology industry before the increase of digital transformation?

To find out to what extent Big Tech companies influence the technology industry before COVID-19, it is important to know what it means when one or more companies have a big influence. When a few companies hold all the power in an industry, it gives them control over the pricing of the products, immense financial reserves and the power to curb newcomers in the industry (Tiwari, 2019).

While studying material regarding Big Tech and their influence on the technology industry before COVID-19, it became clear that most of the information focuses on the negative aspects of Big Tech companies. Fontanel (2019) describes in his paper “GAFAM, a progress and a danger for civilization” multiple critical points about Big Tech. The following points of criticism are illustrated:

- Their sprawling hold on the global economy with their quasi-monopolistic situation;
- The patent-protected applications of technology of domination;
- The commercial use of private information: This information is generated by Big Tech (e.g. Facebook) and won't be publicly available for other companies;
- The creation of a society of control and surveillance of consumers and citizens.

Next to that, Fontanel (2019) indicates that their valuation levels and their ability to raise funds, gives them an exorbitant purchasing power. Big Tech companies can take control of any startup and any promising patent. Tiwari (2019) indicates that the immense financial power and control over the flow of information on the internet, enables Big Tech companies to curb smaller companies that threaten their market share.

What effect does the increase of digital transformation have on the technology industry?

The increase of digital transformation has led to an extra dynamic industry. This can create both opportunities and threats, depending on the demands from “the new common”, such as activities with 1.5-meter distance or online participation (Berret, 2020).

The first change, mentioned in the case is the increasing use of Facebook, Google, Twitter and other social media/platforms. Traffic in this sector

is exploding, due to COVID-19 related information and more dependence on technology (Kshetri, 2020). The increasing sales in technology is considered as the second change. New products are to the majority instead of the early adopters, even late adopters are more likely to be forced to accept some of the technology. This opportunity is most applicable for “effective selling” companies, as figure 2 illustrates below (Kim, 2020).

The major change is the increasing use of videoconferencing platforms, such as Zoom and Microsoft Teams. Videoconferencing is a popular alternative to teach students online, organise meetings or to chat with family and friends (Gaudiot, 2020; Kshetri, 2020). Another consequence is the growing amount of digital subscriptions. Companies such as Netflix see their revenue grow as an effect of the guidelines to stay at home. Lastly, revenues by advertising are decreasing. This can be traced back to the uncertainty of a lot of sectors. Catering industry and tourism have minimal revenue, so there is no budget or motivation to keep spending on advertising. Supply chains are disrupted and most of the companies have to find a new way of working, which will decrease the profit and lead to decreased advertising (Kshetri, 2020).

In brief, there are major opportunities for the technology industry. Companies have to determine if they are delivering the right product during this time within their dynamic market. If the priority is not changing based on the current needs, companies in the technology industry can see their profits decrease at an alarming rate.

Figure 2: Effective selling after COVID-19 (Kim, 2020).

To what extent did the increase of digital transformation affect small businesses in the technology industry?

Research shows that the COVID-19 health crisis forced businesses outside the technology industry to accelerate their digital capabilities and

form a digital agenda to maximize recovery. This acceleration increased the demand for services in the technology industry (Kshetri, 2020). The results of the survey among these small businesses about the effects of increased digital transformation on their business mainly focuses on video calling (81.3%), cloud services (56.3%), live chat (50%) and video platforms (43.8%). The survey shows that small businesses find themselves more and more dependent on the applications and technology of Big Tech companies since the beginning of COVID-19. However, this is not experienced as bothering by 47.5% of the respondents, while 15.8% is neutral.

As stated before, Big Tech companies have the ability to quickly adapt to a changing environment and at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic this was no exception. By optimizing and providing cloud services and video call software, many businesses were able to work from home. The results of the survey showcase that 47% of the respondents disagree that Big Tech companies influence their ability to take advantage of upcoming trends.

To what extent are small businesses in the technology influenced by Big Tech companies?

To get a clear view of the influence of Big Tech companies on small businesses, the focus of this subquestion will be on the trends in the technology industry. To give respondents an indication of which trends are currently relevant in the technology industry, trends indicated by Bugin, J. et al. (2007) were used in the survey. Specific trends that respondents indicated as important are the following:

- Cloud computing;
- Big data;
- Inbound marketing tech;
- Artificial intelligence for personalized customer service (i.e. chatbots, customer service apps);
- Hyper-Personalization.

Research shows that a growth of the technology industry due to the effects of COVID-19, as stated before, will subsequently lead to the growth of Big Tech companies and possibly increase their influence on the trends in the technology industry. Big Tech companies often use their knowledge about individuals in regards to certain topics to gain more financially (Moore, 2016). The opinion of small businesses in the industry on the influence of Big Tech companies on the industry trends are very divided. The differences can be found in the field a small business operates. The results showcase that small businesses in web development, consultancy and software engineering find that Big Tech companies

do not have a negative influence on the ability of small businesses to take advantage of the trends mentioned earlier. 31.6% of the respondents agree that Big Tech have a negative influence, whereas 42.2% disagree. Fields such as travel tech, and ITC/Voice search indicate that Big Tech companies do have a negative influence. However, despite the fact that in some fields Big Tech companies have a negative influence on small businesses to utilize at least one of these trends, 80% of the respondents indicate that they are able and performing at least one of the trends mentioned above.

DISCUSSION

According to the results, the technology industry will grow due to COVID-19, and this has a positive effect on the technology industry, including small businesses. This whereas other industries suffer from the consequences of COVID-19, for instance catering and tourism. While the technology industry gains opportunities, it is essential that businesses determine if they are delivering the right product in this dynamic time and their dynamic market. As is stated, digital subscriptions, the usage of social media platforms, and the usage of applications such as Zoom and Microsoft Team have increased due to the measures (e.g. working at home) taken by governments. The results of the survey also show that as a result of the acceleration of digital capabilities, the demand of services increases. This supports the archival research which states that COVID-19 increased the digital agenda of companies. Interestingly, the survey claims that small businesses disagree that growing influence of Big Tech will negatively influence their growth potential. The explanation for this result is that without the technology of Big Tech companies, many small businesses would not be able to do their work properly.

The allegation mentioned above is contrary to the statement made in sub question one, which states that the immense financial power and control over the flow of information threaten the market share of smaller businesses. Although the power and control can lead to negative consequences, small businesses also claim to have positive effects on their activities.

Validity

The questions of the survey are formulated without any bias and all contain the same Likert Scale (5 point Likert Scale). Nevertheless, the internal validity of this research could be affected by respondents that might give socially desirable answers that do not correspond with their real life actions or feelings (Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2016). The external validity could be affected as a result of the sampling bias. This means that the

sample is not representative for the population. This aspect will be further explained in the limitations of this research.

Judging the validity of this research is done by using SPSS, specifically the corrected Item-Total Correlation. When this item is below 0.3, it indicates that the value is not well correlated. When above 0.3, it means that the item is well correlated. After performing the reliability analysis, six questions have been removed due to low correlation, which would decrease the validity of this measure. The full reliability analysis is shown in Appendix 2, in which the deleted questions have been highlighted. Further limitations on behalf of the reliability will be included in the conclusion of this paper.

Reliability

The survey consists of multi-item measures, Cronbach's alpha is used to measure the reliability of the survey by measuring the internal consistency of a test or scale with a number between 0 and 1. Internal consistency refers to what extent all items in a test measure the same concept or construct and therefore is connected to the inter-relatedness of the items within the test (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). The closer Cronbach's alpha is to 1, the greater the internal consistency of the items in the scale (Gliem & Gliem, 2003). When the Cronbach's alpha is high, it can be stated that the reliability of the measures is high as well. The Cronbach's alpha can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\hat{\alpha} = (k/k - 1) (1 - [\text{Sum of item variances} / (\text{Sum of item variances and covariances})])$$

Figure 3: Basic equation for Cronbach's alpha (Helms et al., 2006).

Performing a reliability analysis in SPSS resulted in a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.819. Looking at George & Mallery's (2003) rule of thumb, this test can be judged as good. This means that the internal consistency of this test is high, which leads to high reliability of the measures. A possibility to improve the Cronbach alpha, if needed, is to delete items that lower the current alpha. However, the results show that no matter which item is deleted, the Cronbach alpha of this test stays above 0.788. Therefore, it is not necessary to delete any items based on the Cronbach Alpha.

CONCLUSION

The paper states that the increase of digital transformation due to COVID-19 measures causes an extra dynamic technology industry for small businesses. Looking back at the subquestions, some

clear changes can be named.

First, most of the literature that describes how Big Tech companies influence the technology industry before the increasing digital transformation focuses on negative impacts. The quasi-monopolistic situation, technology domination, access to private information and control of citizens are named as factors for Big Tech companies to maintain market power. Small businesses are in a difficult position to enter the market.

Secondly, digital transformation leads to an extra dynamic technology industry. The major changes are increasing use of social media, lifting technology sales, growth in video conferencing platforms, more digital subscriptions and a decrease in advertising. The increase of digital transformation creates opportunities and some disadvantages, which can be utilized with "effective selling" (see figure 2). Furthermore, the survey results showed an uplift regarding demand of services in the technology industry, caused by the increased digital transformation. Dependence on applications and technology of Big Tech is growing. Due to the dependence on Big Tech, the influence is not stated as bothersome by almost half of the respondents.

Lastly, the results which show the influence by Big Tech companies on small businesses are divided. In general, the small businesses in web development, consultancy and software engineering are not negative towards Big Tech companies. However, Travel tech and ITC/Voice search answer negatively. This can be explained by their dependency on Big Tech companies.

"What effects do the increase of digital transformation and the influence of Big Tech companies have on small businesses in the technology industry, and to what extent is relationship between the increase of digital transformation and small businesses in the technology industry mediated by the influence of Big Tech companies?"

There are a number of effects of the increase of digital transformation and the influence of Big Tech companies on small businesses in the technology industry. The existence of small businesses in the technology industry would be difficult without the Big Tech companies. The increase of digital transformation is beneficial for small businesses. It causes a growth in the technology industry since the use of technologies becomes increasingly important among businesses in all industries. However, small businesses in the technology industry need to respond correctly to fully benefit from the increase of digital transformation.

As stated before, the growing demand of digital technologies among businesses in all industries causes growth in the technology industry. This growth has increased the dominance of Big Tech companies, since they are the main providers of technical developments. An increase of dominance also increases the influence that Big Tech companies have on small businesses in the technology industry. Thus, the relationship between the increase of digital transformation and small businesses in the technology industry is partially mediated by the influence of Big Tech companies.

LIMITATIONS

The conclusions of this research reduce the existing knowledge gap. The influence of Big Tech companies and the increasing digital transformation on small businesses is clarified, with the positive and negative effects highlighted. However, there are several factors that limit the validity and reliability of this research. Limitations are caused by time and money restrictions. The most important factor is the sample size of the survey. Executing research based on 48 surveys is not enough to generalize the outcomes. Also, the people who responded by email choose to respond voluntarily, which makes it difficult to interpret if the opinions are representative for all small businesses in the technology sector in Holland. Archival research was sufficient to subtract some information, although it was not enough to describe the complexity of the research setting and possible influences. The survey provided relevant insights, but the substantiation of the answers is not included. This makes it hard to assure that the answers are well interpreted by respondents, if they fully understand all the questions and thought they were relevant. In conclusion, the results provide relevant insights since the internal validity of the survey is proven, but the research is not completely valid or reliable.

FURTHER RESEARCH

Since the survey is conducted with the help of existing knowledge, more research would be a valuable addition to verify the findings. Extra primary and secondary research will contribute to the generalizability of the existing research. By conducting further interviews or quantitative research, more explanations can be verified or added to the existing research. For example, unstructured interviews can contribute to the integrality of the research. There can be other relevant factors to add or adjust the existing questions. If the existing research can be validated and completed, it will assure the relevance of this research. Another contribution of further research is the constant updating and expanding of the

existing information, since the magnitude of digital transformation and its effects are constantly changing and cannot be predicted.

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APPENDIX 1: SURVEY QUESTIONS

Introduction
 Thank you for participating in this survey. We are four Pre-Master Information Management students at Tilburg University and we are writing a paper about the influence of Big Tech companies (such as Google, Amazon, Facebook etc.) on tech startups. This paper will contribute knowledge to our conference, TUJODX. This survey is completely anonymous and will take approximately 10 minutes.

General information

1. Name of your company (optional)

2. Expertise of your company/employer

- Biotech
- Health/Personalized health
- On-demand
- Travel Tech
- ITC/Voice search
- Media – VR, TV streaming
- Infrastructure/smart cities
- Other, namely...

3. Amount of employees

4. Years active

Figure 3: Survey questions 1-4.

Topic: Tech startups and the increase of digital transformation

5. Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement:

"The digital transformation due to the effects of COVID-19 changed the operations at my company."

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

6. Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement:

"I found that the adoption of digital applications within my company/employer got a boost due to COVI."

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

7. Which applications have become critical for your daily operations due to the effects of COVID-19 (multiple answers possible)

- Cloud services
- GPS trackers (tracking COVID-19 cases)
- Video calling
- Telemedicine
- Electronic signature devices
- Remote desktop
- Video platforms
- Web portal
- Live chat
- Other, namely...

Figure 4: Survey questions 5-7.

8. Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement:

"I find that my work is more dependent on the applications and technology of Big Tech companies (e.g. Google, Zoom) due to the effects of COVID-19."

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

9. Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement:

"I find it bothering that I (as a startup) am dependent on the applications of Big Tech companies to do work."

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Topic: Trends in the technology industry

10. Please rate the following trends in the technology industry, where 1 indicates no importance at all and 5 very high importance.

	Not important (1)	Slightly important (2)	Moderately important (3)	Important (4)	Very important (5)
Artificial intelligence	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Remote work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Voice recognition technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Big data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Edge computing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Hype-Personalization	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IoT technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 5: Survey questions 8-10.

11. Are there any trends missing in the previous question? (optional)

12. Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement:

"I am utilizing at least one of these trends in my company to its full potential."

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

13. Do you think Big Tech companies have a negative influence on the ability of start-ups to take advantage of these trends?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Topic: Influence of Big Tech companies on start-ups

14. Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement:

"I find that the influence of Big Tech companies on the technology industry is currently too high."

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Figure 6: Survey questions 11-14.

15. Do you think that the abilities of Big Tech, such as the ability to quickly adapt to changing environments and clone products will negatively influence the growth and potential of start-ups?
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
16. Do you think that Big Tech companies offer opportunities for start-ups? E.g. financing projects and providing the ability to work with (free) applications.
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
17. Do you think that Big Tech companies scare tech start-ups off because of their influence?
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree

You have reached the end of our survey. We would like to thank you for your time and participation. If you have any questions regarding this survey or our conference, which will be held January 21st 2021, please send an email to @tilburguniversity.edu.

If you would like to be notified when our paper is published, please enter your email address below. (optional)

Please rate the following trends in the technology industry regarding the influence on small businesses. 1 indicates no importance at all and 5 indicates very important. [Artificial intelligence]	51.63	67.771	.491	.805
Please rate the following trends in the technology industry regarding the influence on small businesses. 1 indicates no importance at all and 5 indicates very important. [Remote work]	50.38	78.495	.146	.822
Please rate the following trends in the technology industry regarding the influence on small businesses. 1 indicates no importance at all and 5 indicates very important. [Voice recognition technology]	52.25	68.745	.559	.800
Please rate the following trends in the technology industry regarding the influence on small businesses. 1 indicates no importance at all and 5 indicates very important. [Big data]	50.75	71.043	.582	.801
Please rate the following trends in the technology industry regarding the influence on small businesses. 1 indicates no importance at all and 5 indicates very important. [Edge computing]	51.94	65.677	.716	.788

Figure 9: Results reliability and validity analysis.

Figure 7: Survey questions 15-17.

APPENDIX 2: RESULTS CRONBACH ALPHA & CORRECTED ITEM-TOTAL CORRELATION

Red marking: Not used in the results due to low validity

No marking: Used in the results

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement: "The digital transformation due to the effects of COVID-19 changed the operations at my company/employer."	50.56	80.166	.005	.828
Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement: "I found that the adoption of digital applications within my company/employer got a boost due to COVID-19."	50.88	79.388	.043	.828
Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement: "I find that my work is more dependent on the applications and technology of Big Tech companies (e.g. Google, Zoom) due to the effects of COVID-19."	50.31	73.113	.570	.804
Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement: "I find it bothering that I am dependent on the applications of Big Tech companies to do my work."	51.75	66.957	.593	.797

Figure 8: Results validity and reliability analysis.

Please rate the following trends in the technology industry regarding the influence on small businesses. 1 indicates no importance at all and 5 indicates very important. [Hyper-Personalization]	51.63	67.133	.719	.790
Please rate the following trends in the technology industry regarding the influence on small businesses. 1 indicates no importance at all and 5 indicates very important. [IoT technology]	51.69	70.943	.475	.806
Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement: "I am utilizing at least one of these trends in my company to its full potential."	50.75	76.532	.279	.816
Do you think Big Tech companies have a negative influence on the ability of small businesses to take advantage of these trends?	51.94	68.613	.551	.800
Please fill in your answer regarding the following statement: "I find that the influence of Big Tech companies on the technology industry is currently too high."	51.50	69.830	.549	.801

Figure 10: Results reliability and validity analysis.

Do you think that the abilities of Big Tech, such as the ability to quickly adapt to changing environments and clone products will negatively influence the growth and potential for small businesses?	51.44	75.060	.238	.820
Do you think that Big Tech companies offer opportunities for small businesses? E.g. financing projects and providing the ability to work with (free) applications.	50.88	81.941	-.119	.837
Do you think that Big Tech companies scare small businesses off because of their big influence?	51.75	69.255	.474	.806

Figure 11: Results reliability and validity analysis.